

Review Article

Biological Activities and Traditional Use of *Hyptis suaveolens* in Human and Veterinary Medicine: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Hyptis suaveolens (*H. suaveolens*), known as Gros baume or sweet-smelling Hyptis, is an invasive plant from tropical regions widely used to manage human and animal ailments, such as bacterial, viral, and parasitic diseases. This study aimed to synthesize scientific research works on the use of this medicinal plant in the traditional pharmacopeia, as well as the biological and pharmacological activities already recognized in the literature. Information for this synthesis was collected from physical (libraries and documentation centers of universities in Benin) and reliable scientific databases, such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science, which were queried based on the keywords related to *H. suaveolens*. This plant contains secondary metabolites in its aerial parts, such as leaves, and stems, which are rich in essential oils. From leaves to roots, all parts of this plant are of interest to both humans and animals to treat various pathologies. The most frequently cited diseases include asthma, paroniasis, jaundice, hyperthermia, indigestion, stomach pains, nausea, colds, gall bladder infections, breast abscesses, hemorrhoids, oral-anal candidiasis, edemas, cramps, and skin infections. The various aqueous and ethanolic extracts are evaluated by researchers and the biological activities are indicated in the literature. Those activities include the antibacterial, antifungal, larvicidal, antioxidant, anticholinesterase, insect repellent, and insecticidal effects. However, no toxicity resulting from the use of this plant has yet been reported in the literature. Research on *H. suaveolens* toxicity must be continued to gain a comprehensive understanding of its application in human and livestock health. This literature review allows the virtues and risks related to the traditional use of *H. suaveolens* in human and animal pharmacopeia. The various potentialities of this plant provide a lever for exploring its antiviral effects in traditional veterinary medicine in general.

1. Introduction

Medicinal plants have been used by mankind since ancient times. However, these practices were neglected with the advent of synthetic chemical processes and the creation of so-called allopathic medicine¹. Today, the multiple public health risks associated with the presence of residues in the food chain or antibiotic resistance have

encouraged the emergence of ethnomedicine². With this in mind, the WHO has urged developing countries to give greater prominence to their traditional pharmacopeia, given that costly modern medicine benefits affluent countries³. The utilization of herbal drugs in human medicine is on the rise¹, a trend observed not only in general human

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healthcare but also in veterinary medicine^{4,5}. This growing adoption of herbal remedies extends to over 80% of the African population at large and is particularly notable in countries like Benin^{6,7}. This rise can be due to the availability of plant resources and the relatively affordable cost of medicinal recipes. The efficiency of certain local recipes in the treatment of several pathologies (infections and parasitic disease), with low side effects for most of them, make them more interesting than synthetic chemical molecules^{8,9}.

In Africa, and particularly in Benin, several studies have highlighted the value of using medicinal plants by livestock farmers to treat their animals¹⁰⁻¹⁶. Thus, the research carried out by Toyang et al.¹⁷ in sub-Saharan Africa provides an overview of ethnomedicinal treatments for several animal diseases¹⁰. One of the commonly used plant resources is *Hyptis suaveolens* (*H. suaveolens*), which has been the subject of many biological, phytochemical, and pharmacological studies, as well as its multiple uses in human and animal nutrition. Some authors have justified that *H. suaveolens* possesses antifungal, anti-infectious, antiparasitic, insecticidal, and insect-repellent activities^{10,18-21}.

Hyptis suaveolens is a highly odorous plant from the Lamiaceae family, greatly reducing biodiversity and pasture productivity²². The essential parts used are the leaves, stems, and roots¹¹, whose analysis of chemical compounds reveals the presence of alkaloids, gallic and catechin tannins, anthocyanins, quinone derivatives, triterpenoids, steroids, mucilages, and reduced compounds¹². The presence of these secondary metabolites in this medicinal plant gives it antiplasmodic, antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, antidiabetic, antirheumatic, antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory, and antiseptic properties in burns and multiple skin complications on both human and animal²³. Although the decoction of *H. suaveolens* roots has a high urosolic acid content (a natural inhibitor of HIV integration)²⁴, antiviral properties of this plant have been reported in the scientific literature.

The present work summarizes studies carried out on *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit, focusing on aspects relating to its biological, pharmacological, and phytochemical use in traditional human and veterinary medicine. This study opens up the prospect of assessing the antiviral effects of

plant extracts on human/animal pathologies in general.

2. Literature

This bibliographic synthesis was based on a literature review that took into account both physical and digital documents relating to *H. suaveolens*. Physical documents were books, doctoral theses, dissertations, newspaper articles, educational magazines, and conference reports available and collected in the libraries and documentation centers of certain Faculties and Schools of the Universities of Abomey-Calavi and Parakou in Benin. The digital documents searched for were obtained by direct contact with the authors and/or via the Internet with search engines such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and Web of Science, assisted by metadata storage systems (Research Gate, Springer Online, Scopus, and Science Direct).

Scientific databases were queried on the basis of keywords relating to *H. suaveolens* and related to "traditional uses", "human medicine", "veterinary medicine", "phytochemical composition", "biological properties", "pharmacological activities" and "toxic effects". This made it possible to download many scientific documents selected based on their titles, abstracts, and keywords. A total count of all the documents downloaded for this synthesis was made in a database (Zotéro), followed by classification according to title. After an analysis, the documents were compiled and selected to retain only those relating to the theme "Synthesis of the biological activities and use of *H. suaveolens* in traditional human and veterinary medicine". 103 publications were recorded in all. After selection, 24 invalid publications (works unrelated to the theme, subject out of context and duplicate documents) were excluded. After analysis and categorization, 79 scientific publications were retained, including 55 original articles, 9 doctoral theses, 8 books, 4 technical reports, and 3 scientific papers. This literature search could determine the virtues and properties of the plant that is the subject of this synthesis.

3. Curve of literature publication

Figure 1 shows the curve of publications in relation to

Figure 1. Number of publications on *Hyptis suaveolens* from 1974 to 2023

their years of notification. The year and the number of publications made on *H. suaveolens* made it possible to obtain an ascending linear regression indicating the evolution of research involving the plant species cited in this bibliographic synthesis. Y corresponds to the number of publications. R^2 is the coefficient of determination that makes measuring the quality of linear adjustment between X and Y possible.

4. Botanical description and geographical distribution

Hyptis suaveolens, also known as *Ballota suaveolens*, is a shrubby plant in the Lamiaceae or Labiatae family, comprising more than 250 genera and nearly 7,000 species spread across the globe, but particularly well represented from the Mediterranean basin to Central Asia²⁵. The *Hyptis* genus is subdivided into three tropical species, including *Hyptis spicigera* Lam, *Hyptis lanceolata* Poir, and *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit. Widespread in tropical Asia and Africa, *H. suaveolens* originated in tropical America and is now found throughout the world's tropical regions²⁶. It is a terrestrial, aromatic annual herb growing up to two meters high. Leaves are simple, entire, petiolate, opposite, and pubescent on both sides. Flowers are purplish in color, hermaphroditic, sessile, and grouped in axillary glomerules. The fruit is a tetrakene containing four seeds clustered at the bottom of the calyx. Field studies have revealed that *H. suaveolens* is a sporadic weed in rice fields^{26,27}. It grows in fallow fields, pastures, undeveloped plots, and along roadsides. Work on production techniques has shown that this plant (Figure 2) grows very easily in West Africa when the direct seeding technique is used^{13,28-30}.

5. Chemical composition

Phytochemical screening of *H. suaveolens* leaves has revealed the presence of all the following families of secondary metabolites, including carbohydrates, alkaloids,

Figure 2. *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit, Source: Phoyographie (Sédégan 2023)

simple sugars, steroids, terpenoids, tannins, flavonoids, anthraquinones, phenols, which account for over 13% of dry leaves mass^{12,31-33}. However, this does not reject the results obtained by Nantitanon et al.²⁰, revealing that the geographical environment is a factor influencing the phytochemical composition of a plant species. *Hyptis suaveolens* leaves contain essential oils³¹ with menthol, limonenes, and sesquiterpenes³⁴, which have numerous pharmacological and biological properties³⁵. Several volatile compounds contained in the leaves of this plant (β -caryophyllene, bergamotene, terpinolene, humulene, sabinene, and limonene) have been reported for the most part as insect repellents and insecticides^{36,37}. Several authors cited by Koné³⁸ have justified that the plant contains a yellow-green etheric oil with hydrocyanic acid, in its roots, barks, and leaves. A phytotoxic substance called suaveolic acid (14 α -hydroxy-13 β -abiet-8-en-18-oic) has been isolated from the methanolic extract of the whole plant of *H. suaveolens*³⁹.

Per 100 g of powder, the yields of dry extracts of chloroformic, ethanolic, and aqueous in *H. suaveolens* leaves were 1.14%, 2.26%, and 4.43%, respectively¹⁹. The highest yield was obtained with aqueous extraction. These chloroformic, ethanolic extracts have a blackish pasty appearance, while the aqueous extract presents a brown-green gummy appearance.

6. Traditional use of *Hyptis suaveolens*

In Africa and tropical zones, *H. suaveolens* is widely used in traditional pharmacopeia to treat a variety of pathologies, the most frequently cited of which are asthma, panariasis, jaundice, hyperthermia, indigestion, stomach pains, nausea, colds, gall bladder infections, breast abscesses, hemorrhoids, candidiasis of the mouth and throat, indigestion, stomach pain, nausea, colds, gallbladder infections, breast abscesses, hemorrhoids, oral-anal candidiasis, edema, cramps, and skin infections^{29,37,40-42}. In Benin, an ethnobotanical survey revealed that *H. suaveolens* is served at 6.1% by market herbalists among plants used to treat infections and 13% among traditional plant users in humans⁴³⁻⁴⁶. These results align with those of Kouhadé et al.¹⁹ indicating that *H. suaveolens* is excellently used in the management of candidiasis and other childhood illnesses and infections. The decoction of its roots is used as an aperitif¹³.

In Côte d'Ivoire and Senegal, alternative pest control methods using aqueous extracts of *H. suaveolens* have been developed^{47,48}. The inflorescences are introduced under mattresses as insecticides, and the smoke released by burning the whole plant is an excellent insect repellent^{48,49}. The *H. suaveolens* extracts are also used in the preparation of mosquitos (mosquito-smoking sticks)⁵⁰. In veterinary ethnomedicine, *H. suaveolens* is also cited among the pharmacological plants recognized and used by livestock breeders in Africa⁵¹. In Benin, it has been observed that the plant is also used by livestock farmers as a healthy food for rodents (rabbits and aulacodes), although its use in animal medicine has received very little attention in the scientific

literature.

7. Biological activities of *Hyptis suaveolens*

The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the essential oils and leaf extracts of *H. suaveolens* were evaluated on a number of microorganisms in order to justify the plant's traditional use. Antimicrobial tests were carried out on dry extracts (aqueous, ethanolic, and chloroformic) and essential oils of the plant on *Staphylococcus (St.) aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia (E.) coli*, *Pasteurella multocida*, *Erysipelothrix rhusiopathia*, *Actinomyces pyogenese*, *Streptococcus suis*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Candida (C.) albicans*, *Trichophyton (T.) mentagrophytes*^{19,20}. The results have revealed that *H. suaveolens* extracts have more antifungal than antibacterial properties.

7.1. Antibacterial activity

The *H. suaveolens* extracts have a strong inhibitory effect on the growth of the bacterial germs studied at a concentration of 20 mgml⁻¹ except for *St. aureus*, which remained only slightly insensitive to certain extracts¹⁹, which confirms the plant's antibacterial potential. Meanwhile, the aqueous extract of *H. suaveolens* proved more active on *E. coli*, *St. aureus*, and *C. albicans*, with zero action on *Salmonella spp.* Agban et al.¹⁹ and Pachkore et al.⁴⁶ showed that the ethanolic extract was more active than the aqueous extract against the growth of *E. coli*. Chitra et al.⁴⁹ found that petroleum ether, chloroform-water, and ethanolic extracts of *H. suaveolens* leaves had strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli*⁴⁹. In contrast, essential oil from the aerial part of *H. suaveolens* has a weak inhibitory effect on *E. coli* growth²⁰. In addition, essential oils from the leaves and ethanolic, etheric and chloroform extracts from the leaves, stems and roots of *Hyptis suaveolens* induced inhibitory effects on the growth of *St. aureus*^{10,20,49}.

7.2. Antifungal activity

The chloroform extract completely inhibited the growth of *C. albicans*, whose minimal inhibition concentration was determined to be 1.25 mgml⁻¹¹⁹. These antifungal tests, which were carried out using the principle of dilution in liquid medium coupled with spreading on agar medium^{19,50} confirm the findings of Kouhadé et al.¹², which stipulate that *H. suaveolens* is more widely used in the management of candidiasis.

Rojas et al.⁵¹ had already reported the antifungal effect of *H. suaveolens* extracts on *C. albicans*, and details of the inhibitory effects on *C. albicans* growth of methanolic, ethanolic, chloroformic, etheric, and aqueous extracts of *H. suaveolens* were shown by Agban et al.¹⁹, Pachkore et al.⁴⁸ and Mbatchou et al.⁵² in their studies. In addition, the antifungal activity of the essential oil of the aerial parts of *H. suaveolens* has been proven on the dermatophytes *T. mentagrophytes*²⁰. It is clear from the above that *H.*

suaveolens is a medicinal plant with antifungal and antibacterial properties that can be exploited.

7.3. Larvicidal (anti-plasmodial) activity

The most widely used method for identifying larvicidal activity of *H. suaveolens* is inspired by the sensitivity test technique standardized by the WHO and adopted for testing larval sensitivity to the drugs used². Generally, non-organic extracts have a higher larvicidal activity than organic extracts. Thus, larvicidal tests carried out with aqueous extracts of 10 plants from the Malian flora, including *H. suaveolens*, gave no mortality of *Anopheles gambiae* larvae⁵³. This confirms the low mortality obtained by Koné³⁵ with organic extracts after 24 hours of exposure despite an increase in concentration to 1,000 µg/mL. In contrast, Aouinty et al.⁵⁴ obtained 100% mortality of *Culex pipiens* larvae in Morocco at a concentration of 1% with aqueous extracts of *Ricinus communis*. This suggests that a plant's lack of larvicidal activity could be justified by its nature and the type of larva.

Koné³⁵ observed total larvicidal activity with the methanolic and ethereal extracts of *H. suaveolens* at 1,000 µg/mL after 24 hours, as well as with the dichloromethane extract, which showed almost total mortality of 97% on *Anopheles gambiae* larvae at the same concentration. The larvicidal activity of *H. suaveolens* varies according to the type of extract, although it appears that alcoholic extracts are highly active on larvae, justifying the results of numerous research studies^{21,53,55,56}. However, a more rapid larvicidal activity on *Anopheles gambiae*, compared with other extracts, was observed with petroleum ether extract, with 100% mortality in one hour³⁸. Similarly, comparing the lethal concentration CL₅₀ of several medicinal plants, Koné³⁸ observed that *H. suaveolens* was even more effective on the larvae, before suggesting that it would be important to study this potentially larvicidal (antiplasmodial) medicinal plant further.

7.4. Anticholinesterase activity

The substances responsible for anticholinesterase activity are present in low quantities in *H. suaveolens* decocts, or are absent from the aerial parts of the plant³⁵. On the other hand, the apolar extract of the plant has demonstrated very good anticholinesterase activity, which decreases with the polarity of the extract³⁸. Greater anticholinesterase activity is observed in extracts that are more apolar. However, Koné³⁸, using the colorimetric method based on the Ellman test, showed in his study that ethereal, dichloromethane and methanolic extracts of *H. suaveolens* proved no remarkable anticholinesterase activity.

In Nigeria, Peter et al.⁵⁷ used Ellman spectrophotometry to demonstrate the anticholinesterase activity of crude methanolic extracts of medicinal plants, with alkaloids as the responsible substances. Similarly, Ferreira et al.⁵⁸ cited alkaloids, terpenes, glycosides, and coumarins as chemical compounds with anticholinesterase properties, Notably, *H.*

suaveolens was found to contain these compounds^{12,31}. In the same study, plants belonging to *Laminaceae* family (*H. suaveolens*) were found to have anticholinesterase properties⁵⁸. All these data justify the acetylcholinesterase-inhibiting activity of the medicinal plant *H. suaveolens*.

7.5. Antioxidant activity

Antioxidants prevent cell damage caused by free radicals normally released during normal metabolism³⁸. They protect the body against cancer and other cardiovascular diseases⁵⁹. In Mali, Koné³⁸ showed that aqueous and methanolic extracts of *H. suaveolens* have reduced the free radical of the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) with very marked antioxidant activity, the results of which are presented as yellow spots on a violet-background plate. The antioxidant action of these different extracts could be explained by their richness in polyphenolic substances, tannins, coumarins, flavonoids and saponosides. In line with the answers given by Bruneton and Cavin^{60,61}, justifying the above-mentioned chemical compounds as potential antioxidants⁶², quoted by Koné³⁸, justifies the antioxidant activity of *H. suaveolens* as a substance rich in flavonoids (antioxidant substances active in maintaining blood circulation, as they contribute to increasing the production of nitric oxide by blood platelets, which limits clot formation by preventing platelets from clumping together).

7.6. Insect repellent and insecticide

Hyptis suaveolens is a plant species with both insecticidal and repellent properties⁶³⁻⁶⁵, for the control of insect pests of field crops. It is a massively cultivated plant in regions of Africa where nuisance mosquitoes, vectors of disease, are rife¹⁸. The aerial parts of the plant are used as a safe mosquito repellent, as they show no human toxicity^{18,66}. A study by Azeez⁶⁵ indicated that *H. suaveolens* powder causes significant mortality (100%) in invertebrates (*Callosobruchus maculatus*) after 7 days of treatment.

In Senegal, *H. suaveolens* inflorescences are introduced under mattresses to repel adult mosquitoes. Similarly, Sane⁴⁴ has shown that the drop in the number of *H. armigera* caterpillars in cotton plots treated with aqueous extracts of *H. suaveolens* is due to the plant's repellent and insecticidal properties. The repellent action is also due to the volatile substances emitted by the plant, which contains essential oils with contact toxicity and a positive repellent effect at low doses⁶⁸. These essential oils contain active compounds such as geraniol, 1,8 cineole, linalool, myrcene, limonene, and phellandrene, which possess insecticidal properties⁶⁹. This was confirmed by Conti et al.⁷⁰ reporting that *H. suaveolens* essential oils have a repellent activity on *Sitophilus granarius* adults due to the presence of molecules such as 1,8 cineole, carvacrol, α -pinene and β -pinene. Guèye et al.⁷¹ were able to preserve corn cobs for 7 months without insect attack by a system alternating layers of corn with *H. spicigera* leaves, then it could be

asserted that *H. suaveolens* possessed the same protective effects on cereals against harmful insects. Similarly, an extract of *H. suaveolens* has been shown to effectively control maize pests, notably *Mussidia nigrivenella* Ragonot⁷²⁻⁷⁴. The work of Kossou et al.⁶³ demonstrated that the aqueous extract of fresh *H. suaveolens* leaves could exert a lethal action on adults and larvae. This effect was also confirmed by Tano et al.⁴³ and Tounou et al.⁷⁵, who reported the efficacy of aqueous extract of *H. suaveolens* leaves on the caterpillars of *Hellula undalis*, and *Maruca vitrata*, pests of the cabbage crop.

8. Other biological activities

Several other activities of *H. suaveolens*, linking anti-inflammatory, antinociceptive, antiulcer, antidiabetic, antirheumatic, antisyphilitic, antiseptic, antitarrhal, cutaneous antiparasitic and cytotoxicity properties have been reported in the literatures^{23,76-78}. In addition, aqueous extracts of *H. suaveolens* leaves have been shown to be effective against green pepper mottle virus and its vector (*aphids*)⁷⁷, and the decoction of its roots is reputed to contain urosolic acid, a natural inhibitor of HIV integration²⁴.

9. Prospect for usage and issues

In Africa as a tropical zone, *H. suaveolens* is a medicinal plant widely used in traditional pharmacopoeia to treat a variety of contagious and non-contagious pathologies, both infectious and parasitic^{14,29,37,40-42}. In Benin, Kouchadé et al.¹⁸ have shown that *H. suaveolens* is excellently used in the treatment of candidiasis and other childhood illnesses. The decoction of its roots is also used as an aperitif²⁴. In traditional veterinary pharmacopoeia, *H. suaveolens* has been little cited among the plants for pharmacological use recognized and used by livestock farmers in Africa⁴⁷. Nevertheless, in southern Benin, Sèdégan et al.¹⁵ reported that traditional poultry farmers had identified and used *H. suaveolens* leaves and stems in the treatment of fowl pox, with mixed results. These poor results could be explained by a lack of knowledge of the plant's gallic forms of use and consequently of its therapeutic doses. Studies on the use of medicinal plants need to be broadened to include phytochemical, pharmacological¹² and pharmacotoxicological aspects for better rationalization of administration doses¹⁶. Hence, this bibliographic synthesis is important because it will better understand the chemical compounds of *H. suaveolens*, its various biological and pharmacological activities, and its oral toxicity. As a result, the practice of phytotherapy and aromatherapy is growing in human and veterinary medicine¹. Involvement of this bibliographic synthesis today, a new boom in natural medicine has become a reality, linked to the development of organic farming and, above all, the search for new anti-infective molecules as alternatives to synthetic antibiotics to combat the emergence of resistance induced by their misuse⁷⁹. These practices are increasingly sought-after, despite the still small number of scientific studies carried out on the subject.

However, this bibliographic synthesis provides a broad knowledge of the therapeutic use of *H. suaveolens* in traditional medicine.

10. Conclusion

Hyptis suaveolens is a medicinal plant widely used in the traditional human and veterinary pharmacopeia. All parts of the plant (leaves, stems, and roots) are used for a variety of purposes. Phytochemical tests and biological effects have been extensively discussed by several authors. The plant has been the subject of several studies, the results of which have had a positive impact on its pharmacological character through its antioxidant, antibacterial, skin antiparasitic, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anticholinesterase, and larvicidal activities. Its insecticidal and insect-repellent effects rival many synthetic chemical insecticides on the market. However, the antiviral effects of this species in relation to veterinary medicine have not yet been addressed. In view of these scientifically proven therapeutic virtues, *in vivo* and *in vitro* testing of the various extracts of *H. suaveolens* must continue with a view to manufacturing phytomedicines from this plant. The results of work carried out on the traditional use of *H. suaveolens*, as well as the biological and pharmacological activities justified in favor of this medicinal plant, should provide relief to those involved in traditional medicine.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

Bienvenue Sèdégan, Yao Akpo, Cyrille Boko, and Guy Apollinaire Mensah developed the design plan for this literature review. All authors participated in the collection of data. Bienvenue Sèdégan drafted the article, assisted by Christophe Iwaka and Alassan Assani Seidou. The critical observations of the article and its final approval were provided by Yao Akpo, Cyrille Boko, Eloi Attakpa, Guy Apollinaire Mensah, and Ibrahim Alkoiret. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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Availability of data and materials

All data are included within the article.

Ethical considerations

Neither this literature review nor any part of the manuscript has been published in any form elsewhere. All authors are in agreement with the content of the

manuscript and its original submission to the journal.

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References

1. Bruselle M. Mise en place D'AMM allégée en phytothérapie vétérinaire; conséquences probable sur la pratique de la phytothérapie en médecine vétérinaire [Implementation of reduced marketing authorization for veterinary phytotherapy; probable consequences on the practice of phytotherapy in veterinary medicine]. Thèse de doctorat vétérinaire, Université de Lyon, France. 2017.
2. World health organization (WHO). Strategies for malaria control in the African region and steps for their implementation. Cahiers Techniques AFRO. 2013; p. 1-20.
3. Adjanohoun EJ, Ake Assi L, Floret JJ, Guinko S, Koumaré M, Ahyi AMR, et al. Médecine traditionnelle et pharmacopée, contribution aux études ethnobotaniques et floristiques du Mali. [Traditional medicine and pharmacopoeia, a contribution to ethnobotanical and floristic studies in Mali] 3rd ed. Paris: ACCT; 1981. p. 1 - 291.
4. Tamboura HH, Kaboré H, and Yaméogo SM. Ethnomédecine vétérinaire et pharmacopée traditionnelle dans le plateau central du Burkina Faso: cas de la province du Passoré. [Veterinary ethnomedicine and traditional pharmacopoeia in the central plateau of Burkina Faso: The case of the Passoré Province.] Biotechnol Agron Soc Environ. 1998; 2(3): 181-191.
5. Centre d'analyse des politiques économiques et sociales (CAPES). Etat des lieux des savoirs locaux au Burkina Faso. Inventaire des bonnes pratiques et propositions pour leur contribution au développement [Inventory of local knowledge in Burkina Faso. Inventory of good practices and proposals for their contribution to development]. CAPES: Ouagadougou; 2006, p. 1 - 448.
6. WORLD health organization (WHO). WHO traditional medicine strategy 2014-2023. Geneva: WHO; 2014-2023. p. 1-65. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241506096>
7. WORLD health organization (WHO). Report of the WHO interregional workshop on the use of traditional medicine in primary health care. Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, 2007. p. 94. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241597425>
8. Ali M, Ravinder E, and Ramachandran R. A new flavonoid from the aerial parts of *Tridax procumbens*. Fitoterapia. 2001; 72(3): 313-315. DOI: [10.1016/S0367-326X\(00\)00296-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0367-326X(00)00296-3)
9. Zerbo P, Millogo-Rasolodimby J, Nacoulma-Ouedraogo OG, and Damme PV. Contribution à la connaissance des plantes médicinales utilisées dans les soins infantiles en pays San, au Burkina Faso [Contribution to the knowledge of medicinal plants used in infant care in San country, Burkina Faso]. Int J Biol Chem Sci. 2007; 1: 262-274. DOI: [10.4314/ijbcs.v1i3.39704](https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v1i3.39704)
10. Pachkore GL, Dhale DA, and Dharasurkar AN. Antimicrobial and phytochemical screening of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.Poit) Lamiaceae. Internat Multidiscipl Res J. 2011; 1(4): 1-3. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/236014589.pdf>
11. Adomou AC, Yedomonhan H, Djossa B, Legba I, Oumorou M, and Akoegninou A. Etude ethnobotanique des plantes médicinales vendues dans le marché d'Abomey-Calavi au Bénin [Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants sold in the Abomey-Calavi market in Benin]. Int J Biol Chem Sci. 2012; 6(2): 745-772. DOI: [10.4314/ijbcs.v6i2.18](https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v6i2.18)
12. Kouchadé SA, Adjatin AR, Adomou AC, Dassou HG, and Akoegninou A. Phytochimiques des plantes médicinales utilisées dans la prise en charge des maladies infantiles au Sud Bénin [Phytochemicals of medicinal plants used to treat childhood illnesses in southern Benin]. Euro Sci J. 2017; 3(1). DOI: [10.19044/esj.2016.v13n3p471](https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2016.v13n3p471)
13. Ahoton LE, Alavo TBC, Ahomadegbe MA, Ahanhanzo C, and Agbangla C. Domestication du gros baume (*Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit.):

- Techniques de production et potentiels insectes ravageurs au sud du Bénin [Domestication of coarse balsam (*Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit.): Production techniques and potential insect pests in southern Benin]. *Int J Biol Chem Sci.* 2010; 4(3): 608-614. DOI: [10.4314/ijbcs.v4i3.60463](https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v4i3.60463)
14. Singh HB, and Handique AK. Antifungal activity of the essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens* and its efficacy in biocontrol measures in combination with *Trichoderma harzianum*. *J Essent Oil Res.* 1997; 9: 683-687. DOI: [10.1080/10412905.1997.9700811](https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.1997.9700811)
 15. Sédégan B, Akpo Y, Boko C, Attakpa E, and Alkoiret I. Perception des aviculteurs traditionnels sur la maladie de variole aviaire au sud Bénin [Traditional poultry farmers' perceptions of fowl pox in southern Benin]. *Rev Mar Sci Agron Vét.* 2023a; 11(1): 107-112. Available at: https://www.agrimaroc.org/index.php/Actes_IJVH2/article/view/1280/1724
 16. Sédégan B, Akpo Y, Boko C, Iwaka C, Attakpa E, and Alkoiret I. Méthodes chimiques et alternatives de lutte contre la variole dans les élevages de poulet : Synthèse bibliographique [Chemical and alternative control methods for smallpox on chicken farms: A literature review]. *BRAB.* 2023b; 33(3): 79-88. Available at: <https://publications-chercheurs.inrab.bj/uploads/fichiers/receints/18027c76fc5ac2113975623f5c783d12.pdf>
 17. Toyang NJ, Wanyama J, Nuwanyakpa M, and Django S. Ethnomédecine vétérinaire: une approche pratique du traitement des maladies du bétail en Afrique subsaharienne [Veterinary ethnomedicine: A practical approach to the treatment of livestock diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa]. Wageningen: Agrodok; 2007. Available at: <https://duddal.org/s/bibnum-promap/item/3981>
 18. Abagli AZ, Alavo TBC, Avlessi F, and Moudachirou M. Potential of bush mint, *hyptis suaveolens*, essential oil for personal protection against mosquitoes bitings. *J Am Mosq Control Assoc.* 2012; 28(1): 15-19. DOI: [10.2987/11-6181.1](https://doi.org/10.2987/11-6181.1)
 19. Agban A, Atchou K, Tchacondo T, Hoekou YP, Batawila K, and de Souza C. Potentiel antimicrobien des extraits de feuilles de *Hyptis suaveolens* poit [Antimicrobial potential of *Hyptis suaveolens* poit leaf extracts]. *J Rech Sci Univ Lomé Série A.* 2013; 15(3): 37-44. Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jrsul/article/view/121170>
 20. Nantitanon W, Chowwana PS, and Okonogi S. Antioxydant and antimicrobienne activité de *Hyptis suaveolens* essential oil. *Sci Pharm.* 2007; 75: 35-36. DOI: [10.3797/scipharm.2007.75.35](https://doi.org/10.3797/scipharm.2007.75.35)
 21. Diallo D, Marston A, Terreaux C, Touré Y, Paulsen B, and Smestad HK. Screening of malian medicinal plants for antifungal, larvicidal, molluscicidal, antioxydant and radical scavenging activities. *Phytother Res.* 2011; 15: 401-406. DOI: [10.1002/ptr.738](https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.738)
 22. Ouedraogo RL, Thiombiano N, Belem M, and Guinko S. Dynamique de l'évolution et impact d'une plante envahissante au Burkina Faso: *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) poit [Evolutionary dynamics and impact of an invasive plant in Burkina Faso: *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) poit]. *Ann Univ Lomé (Togo), série Sciences, Tome XVIII.* 2009. p. 97-115.
 23. Grassi P, Reyes TSU, Sosac S, Tubaroc A, Hoferd O, and Zitterl-Eglsseer K. Anti-inflammatory activity of two diterpenes of *hyptis suaveolens* from El Salvador. *Z Naturforsch C.* 2006; 61(3-4): 165-170. DOI: [10.1515/znc-2006-3-402](https://doi.org/10.1515/znc-2006-3-402)
 24. Moreira ACP, Lima EO, Wanderley PA, Carmo ES, and de Souza EL. Chemical composition and antifungal activity of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit leaves essential oil against *Aspergillus* species. *Braz J Microbiol.* 2010; 41: 28-33. DOI: [10.1590/S1517-83822010000100006](https://doi.org/10.1590/S1517-83822010000100006)
 25. TOIL' D'EPICES. Epices, condiments et herbes aromatiques [Spices, condiments and aromatic herbs]. D'après. The plant book, 2nd ed. 2006. Available at: <https://planet-vie.ens.fr/thematiques/cellules-et-molecules/molecules/epices-et-herbes-aromatiques>
 26. Johnson F, Ouossou KR, Kanko C, Tonzibo ZF, Foua-bi K, and Tano Y. Bioefficacité des Huiles Essentielles de Trois Espèces végétales (*Ocimum gratissimum*, *Ocimum canum* et *Hyptis suaveolens*), de la Famille des Labiées dans la lutte contre *Sitophilus zeamais* [Bioefficacy of essential oils of three plant species (*Ocimum gratissimum*, *Ocimum canum* and *Hyptis suaveolens*) of the labiées family in the fight against *sitophilus zeamais*]. *Eur J Sci Res.* 2018; 150(3): 273-284.
 27. Soro D, Koné MW, and Kamanzi AK. Evaluation des Activités Antimicrobiennes et Anti-Radicaux Libres de Quelques Taxons Bioactifs de Côte d'Ivoire. [Evaluation of the Antimicrobial and Free Anti-Radical Activities of Selected Bioactive Taxa from Côte d'Ivoire]. *Eur J Sci Res.* 2010; 40(2): 307-317.
 28. Arthur C. The evolution and classification of flowering plants. *Madroño.* 2077-78. Available at: <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/part/170449>
 29. Sharma PP, Roy RK, Anurag GD, and Vipin KS. *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) poit: A phyto-pharmacological review. *Int J Chem Pharm Sci.* 2013; 4(1): 1-11. Available at: http://www.ijcps.com/sub_pages/vol4issue1.html
 30. Aboh BA. Phytosociologie, écologie, potentialités et aménagement des pâturages naturels envahis par *Chromolaena odorata* et *Hyptis suaveolens* en Zone Soudano-guinéenne (Bénin) [Phytosociology, ecology, potential and management of natural pastures invaded by *Chromolaena odorata* and *Hyptis suaveolens* in the Sudano-Guinean zone (Benin)]. Thèse de Doctorat, Université d'Abomey-Calavi, Bénin. 2008. Available at: <http://www.slire.net/document/1625>
 31. Soumahoro B, Soro Y, Kassi ABB, and Siaka S. Etude comparative des caractéristiques phytochimiques des feuilles de *Hyptis suaveolens* avant et après extraction de l'huile essentielle [Comparative study of the phytochemical characteristics of *Hyptis suaveolens* leaves before and after extraction of the essential oil]. *J Soc Ouest-Afr Chim.* 2020; 49: 1-8. Available at: <https://www.soachim.info/document/journal-soachim/article/Vol-049Num-1-f9c453dc515f01983959cc4f0643fac.pdf>
 32. Goly KRC, Soro Y, Dadié A, Kassi ABB, and Djé M. Antibacterial activity of essential oils and extracts from the leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* and *Lippia multiflora* on multi-resistant bacteria. *Rasayan J Chem.* 2015; 8(4): 396-403. Available at: https://rasayanjournal.co.in/vol-8/issue-4/1_Vol.8,%20No.4,%20396-403,%20Oct-Dec,%202015,%20RJC%201345.pdf
 33. Kumar SN, and Thampi N. Phytochemical screening and characterization of the bioactive compounds from the leaves of *Hyptis suaveolens* and *Spathodea campanulata*. *J Chem Pharm Res.* 2015; 7(7): 840-850.
 34. Tia EV, Adima AA, Niamké SL, Jean GA, Martin T, Lozano P, et al. Chemical composition and insecticidal activity of essential oils of two aromatic plants from Ivory Coast against *Bemisia tabaci* G. (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). *Nat Prod Commun.* 2011; 6(8): 1183-1188. DOI: [10.1177/1934578X1100600835](https://doi.org/10.1177/1934578X1100600835)
 35. Mandal SM, Mondal KC, Dey S, and Pati BR. Antimicrobial activity of the leaf extracts of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) poit. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2007; 69(4): 568-569. DOI: [10.4103/0250-474X.36946](https://doi.org/10.4103/0250-474X.36946)
 36. Jaenson TGT, Pålsson K, and Borg-Karlson AK. Evaluation of extracts and oils of mosquito (Diptera : Culicidae) repellent plants from Sweden and Guinea-Bissau. *J Med Entomol.* 2006; 43(1) :113-119. DOI: [10.1093/jmedent/43.1.113](https://doi.org/10.1093/jmedent/43.1.113)
 37. Peerzada N. Chemical composition of the essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens*. *Int J Molecules.* 1997; 2: 165-168. DOI: [10.3390/21100165](https://doi.org/10.3390/21100165)
 38. Koné MD. Etude de la phytochimie et des activités larvicide, anticholinestérasique et antioxydante des extraits de quatre plantes du Mali : *Acacia nilotica* Guill. et Perr. (Mimosaceae), *Calotropis procera* (Ait.) Ait.f. (Asclepiadaceae), *Euphorbia sudanica* A. Chev (Euphorbiaceae) et *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit (Lamiaceae) [Study of the phytochemistry and larvicidal, anticholinesterase and antioxidant activities of extracts from four plants from Mali: *Acacia nilotica* Guill. et Perr. (Mimosaceae), *Calotropis procera* (Ait.) Ait.f. (Asclepiadaceae), *Euphorbia sudanica* A. Chev (Euphorbiaceae) and *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit (Lamiaceae)]. Thèse de doctorat. Année University, France. 2009. Available at: <https://bibliosante.ml/handle/123456789/7082?locale-attribute=en>
 39. Islam AKMM, Ohno O, Suenaga K, and Kato-Noguchi H. Suaveolic acid: A potent phytotoxic substance of *hyptis suaveolens*. *Sci World J.* 2014; 2014: 425942. DOI: [10.1155/2014/425942](https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/425942)
 40. Azevedo NR, Campos IF, Ferreira HD, Portes TA, Santos SC, Seraphin JC, et al. Chemical variability in the essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens*. *Phytochemistry.* 2001; 57(5): 733-736. DOI: [10.1016/S0031-9422\(01\)00128-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(01)00128-5)
 41. Fun CE, and Svendsen AB. The essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens* Poit. grown on Aruba. *Flav Fragr J.* 1990; 5: 161-163. DOI: [10.1002/ffj.2730050306](https://doi.org/10.1002/ffj.2730050306)
 42. Koudokpon H, Dougnon VT, Bankolé HS, Fah L, Hounmanou YMG, Baba-moussa L, et al. Enquête ethnobotanique sur les plantes utilisées dans le traitement des infections au Sud-Bénin [Ethnobotanical survey of plants used to treat infections in southern Benin]. *Health Sci Dis.* 2017; 18(2): 92-99. Available at: [17](http://www.hsd-

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- [fmsb.org/index.php/hsd/article/view/809/pdf_436](https://www.fmsb.org/index.php/hsd/article/view/809/pdf_436)
43. Tano DK, Christian NOR, N'Guessan AP, Obodji A, N'Guessan Y, and Lucie ALRN. Effet insecticide des extraits aqueux de deux plantes sur *hellula undalis fabricius*, 1781 (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), ravageur de la culture de chou brassica oleracea L. (Daloa, Côte d'Ivoire) [Insecticidal effect of aqueous extracts of two plants on *hellula undalis fabricius*, 1781 (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), pest of cabbage crop brassica oleracea L. (Daloa, Ivory Coast)]. Eur J Sci Res. 2019; 2(10) : 168-180.
 44. Sane. Efficacité biologique des extraits d'*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit et *Anacardium occidentale* Linn. dans la lutte contre *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner, 1808) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) ravageur du cotonnier (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) au Sénégal [Biological efficacy of extracts of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit and *Anacardium occidentale* Linn. in the control of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner, 1808) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) pest of cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) in Senegal]. Thèse de doctorat en Entomologie Université Cheikh Anta Diop de Dakar. 2021.
 45. Seyoum A, Kabiru EW, Lwande W, Killeen GF, Hassanali A, and Knols BG. Repellency of live potted plants against *Anopheles gambiae* from human baits in semi-field experimental huts. Am J Trop Med Hyg. 2002; 67(2) : 191-195. DOI: [10.4269/ajtmh.2002.67.191](https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.2002.67.191)
 46. Kerharo J, and Adam JG. La pharmacopée sénégalaise traditionnelle : plantes médicinales et toxiques [Traditional Senegalese pharmacopoeia: Medicinal and toxic plants]. Journal d'agriculture traditionnelle et de botanique appliquée. 1974; 21(1-3): 76-77. Available at: https://www.persee.fr/doc/jatba_0021-7662_1974_num_21_1_3153_t1_0076_0000_2
 47. Byavu N, Henrard C, Dubois M, and Malaisse F. Phytothérapie traditionnelle des bovins dans les élevages de la plaine de la Ruzizi [Traditional herbal medicine for cattle on the Ruzizi plain]. Agron Soc Environ. 2000; 4(3): 135-156. Available at: <https://popups.uliege.be/1780-4507/index.php?id=15244>
 48. Pachkore GL, Dhale DA, and Dharasurkar AN. Antimicrobial and phytochemical screening of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.Poit) Lamiaceae. Internat Multidiscipl Res J. 2011; 1(4): 1-3. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/236014589.pdf>
 49. Chitra S, Patil MB, and Ravi k. Wound healing activity of *hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit (Lamiaceae). Int J Pharm Tech Res. 2009; 1(3): 737-744.
 50. de Souza C, Ameganvi KK, Koumaglo K, and Gbeassor M. Etude de l'activité antimicrobienne des extraits aqueux totaux de dix plantes médicinales [Study of the antimicrobial activity of total aqueous extracts of ten medicinal plants]. PMTA . 1993; 2(7): 107-115.
 51. Rojas A, Hernandez L, Pereda-Miranda R, and Mata R. Screening for antimicrobial activity of crude drug extracts and pure natural products from Mexican medicinal plants. J Ethnopharmacol. 1992; 35(3): 75-83. DOI: [10.1016/0378-8741\(92\)90025-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741(92)90025-M)
 52. Mbatchou VC, Abdullatif S, and Glover R. Phytochemical screening of solvent extracts from *Hyptis suaveolens* Lam for fungal growth inhibition. Pak J Nutr. 2010; 9(4): 358-361. DOI: [10.3923/pjn.2010.358.361](https://doi.org/10.3923/pjn.2010.358.361)
 53. Bah S. Sensibilité de *Anopheles gambiae* aux insecticides organiques de synthèse et à divers extraits de plantes médicinales du Mali [Sensitivity of *Anopheles gambiae* to synthetic organic insecticides and various medicinal plant extracts from Mali]. Thèse de Doctorat en Pharmacie, University of Bamako, Mali. 1998. Available at: <https://bibliosante.ml/handle/123456789/12017?show=full>
 54. Aouinty B, Oufara S, Mellouki F, and Mahari S. Evaluation préliminaire de l'activité larvicide des extraits aqueux des feuilles de *Ricinus communis* L. et du bois de *Tetraclinis articulata* (Vahl) Mast. sur les larves de quatre moustiques culicidés : *Culex pipiens* (Pallas), *Culiseta longiareolata* (Aitken) et *Anopheles maculipennis* [Preliminary evaluation of the larvicidal activity of aqueous extracts of *Ricinus communis* L. leaves and *Tetraclinis articulata* (Vahl) Mast. wood on the larvae of four culicid mosquitoes: *Culex pipiens* (Pallas), *Culiseta longiareolata* (Aitken) and *Anopheles maculipennis*]. (Meigen). Biotechnol Agron Soc Environ. 2006; 10(2): 67-71. Available at: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/20063124498>
 55. Diakité B. La susceptibilité des larves de *Anopheles gambiae* s.l. à des extraits de plantes médicinales du Mali [The susceptibility of larvae of *Anopheles gambiae* s.l. to medicinal plant extracts from Mali]. Thèse de Doctorat en Pharmacie, University of Bamako, Mali. 2008. Available at: <https://bibliosante.ml/bitstream/handle/123456789/8282/08M147.pdf?sequence=1>
 56. Sharma N, Quadry JS, Subrabani B, Verghese T, Rahman SS, Sharma SK, et al. Larvicidal activity of *Gliricidia sepium* against mosquito larvae of *Anopheles stephansi*, *Aedes aegypti* and *Culex quinquefasciatus* [Larvicidal activity of *Gliricidia sepium* against mosquito larvae of *Anopheles stephansi*, *Aedes aegypti* and *Culex quinquefasciatus*]. Pharm Biol. 1998; 36(1): 3-7. DOI: [10.1076/phbi.36.1.3.4616](https://doi.org/10.1076/phbi.36.1.3.4616)
 57. Houghton PJ, Agbedakunsi JM, and Adegbulugbe A. Cholinesterase inhibitory properties of alkaloids from two Nigerian Crinum species. Phytochemistry. 2004; 65(21): 2893-2896. DOI: [10.1016/j.phytochem.2004.08.052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2004.08.052)
 58. Ferreira A, Proença C, Serralheiro MLM, and Araújo MEM. The *in vitro* screening for acetylcholinesterase inhibition and antioxidant activity of medicinal plants from Portugal. J Ethnopharmacol. 2006; 108: 31-37. DOI: [10.1016/j.jep.2006.04.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2006.04.010)
 59. Pincemail J, Meurisse M, Limet R, and Defraigne J. Méthodes d'évaluation du stress oxydant chez l'homme: Importance en matière de prévention. Cancérologie Ed Medi Sphere [Methods for assessing antioxidant stress in humans: Importance in prevention. Oncology Ed Medi Sphere]. 1999.
 60. Bruneton J. Pharmacognosie et phytochimie des plantes médicinales [Pharmacognosy and phytochemistry of medicinal plants]. 2nd ed. Paris: Lavoisier; 1993.
 61. Cavin A. Investigation phytochimique des trois plantes indonésiennes aux propriétés antioxydantes et antiradicalaires: *Tinospora crisa* (Menispermaceae), *Merremia emarginata* (Convolvulaceae) et *Oreophea eneandra* (Annonaceae) [Phytochemical investigation of three Indonesian plants with antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties: *Tinospora crisa* (Menispermaceae), *Merremia emarginata* (Convolvulaceae) and *Oreophea eneandra* (Annonaceae)]. -Thèse de doctorat, Année University, France. 1999. <https://bibliosante.ml/bitstream/handle/123456789/6828/05P21.pdf?sequence=1>
 62. Fiol M, Adermann S, Neugart S, Rohn S, Mügge C, Schreiner M, et al. Highly glycosylated and acylated flavonols isolated from kale (*Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica*) - Structure -antioxidant activity relationship. Food Res Int. 2012; 47: 80-89. DOI: [10.1016/j.foodres.2012.01.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2012.01.014)
 63. Kossou KD, Gbehounou G, Bouraima Y, Huis A, Ahanchede A, Ahoheundo B, et al. Extrait aqueux de *Hyptis suaveolens* plante nouvellement identifiée au Bénin pour le contrôle des insectes nuisibles du niébé au champ [Aqueous extract of *Hyptis suaveolens*, a plant newly identified in Benin, for the control of insect pests of cowpea in the field]. Projet Niébé BJ 002906, Bénin. 2000. p. 32.
 64. Ngom S, Perez RC, Mbow MA, Fall R, Niassy S, Cosoveanu A, et al. Larvicidal activity of Neem oil and three plant essential oils from Senegal against *Chrysodeixis chalcites* (Esper, 1789). Asian Pac J Trop Biomed. 2018; 8(1): 67-72. DOI: [10.4103/2221-1691.221140](https://doi.org/10.4103/2221-1691.221140)
 65. Cherry R, and Nuessly G. Repellency of the biopesticide, *Azadirachtin*, to wireworms (*Coleoptera: Elateridae*). Fla Entomol. 2010; 93(1): 52-55. DOI: [10.1653/024.093.0107](https://doi.org/10.1653/024.093.0107)
 66. Attawish A, Chivapat S, Chavalittumrong P, Phadungpat S, Bandiddhi J, and Chaorai B. Chronic toxicity study of *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit in rats. Songklanakarin J Sci Technol. 2005; 27(5): 1027-1036.
 67. Azeez OM, and Pitan OOR. Sole and combined effect of three botanicals against cowpea seed bruchid, *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius. Afr J Agric Res. 2018; 13(7): 321-328. DOI: [10.5897/AJAR2017.12737](https://doi.org/10.5897/AJAR2017.12737)
 68. Belder Den E, Elderson J, and Agca I. Host finding of thrips *tabaci* disrupted by volatiles. Department of Crop Production Ecology, Wageningen University, Netherlands, 1998.
 69. Ngamo TSL, Ngatanko I, Ngassoum MB, Mapongmestsem PM, and Hance T. Persistence of insecticidal activities of crude essential oils of three aromatic plants towards four major stored product insect pests. Afr J Agric Res. 2007; 2(4): 173-177. Available at: <https://academicjournals.org/journal/AJAR/article-full-text-pdf/491C5DE30606>
 70. Conti B, Canale A, Cioni PL, Flamini G, and Rifici A. *Hyptis suaveolens* and *Hyptis spicigera* (Lamiaceae) essential oils: qualitative analysis, contact toxicity and repellent activity against *Sitophilus granarius* (L.) (Coleoptera: Dryophthoridae). J Pest Sci. 2011; 84: 219-228. DOI: [10.1007/s10340-010-0343-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-010-0343-0)

71. Guèye MT, Diallo A, Guèye S, Seck D, Assiedu E, Wathelet JP, et al. Analysis of the composition of plant essential oil used in cereals and legumes storage in Senegal. *J Essent Oil Bear Pl.* 2016 ; 19(2) : 403-409. DOI: [10.1080/0972060X.2014.935019](https://doi.org/10.1080/0972060X.2014.935019)
72. Gbedomon CR, Sikirou R, Zannou E, Pomalegni SCB, Goergen G, Bokonon-Ganta H, et al. Extraits botaniques utilisés contre les arthropodes associés aux abeilles et produits de la ruche inventoriés dans les ruchers au centre du Bénin [Botanical extracts used against bee-associated arthropods and hive products inventoried in apiaries in central Benin]. *Actes du 3ème Colloque des Sciences, Cultures et Technologies de l'UAC-Bénin*, 2012; pp. 573-588.
73. Adda C, Atachi P, Hell K, and Tamo M. Potential use of the bushmint, *Hyptis suaveolens*, for the control of infestation by the pink stalk borer, *Sesamia calamistis* on maize in southern Benin, West Africa. *J Insect Sci.* 2011; 11(1): 33. DOI: [10.1673/031.011.0133](https://doi.org/10.1673/031.011.0133)
74. Agboka K, Agbodzavu KM, Tomò M, and Vidal S. Effects of plant extracts and oil emulsions on the maize cob borer *Mussidia nigricornis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) in laboratory and field experiments. *Int J Trop Insect Sci.* 2009; 29(4): 185-194. DOI: [10.1017/S1742758409990348](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742758409990348)
75. Tounou AK, Sokame BM, Akpavi S, Ganyo KK, Ketoh KG, and Gumedzoe YMD. Effets des extraits végétaux sur la dynamique de populations des insectes ravageurs de niébé, *vigna unguiculata* Walp, dans le sud du Togo [Effects of plant extracts on the population dynamics of insect pests of cowpea, *vigna unguiculata* Walp, in southern Togo]. *J Rech Sci Univ Lomé.* 2012; 14(1): 25-34. Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jrsul/article/view/86754#:~:text=Des%20r%C3%A9sultats%20de%20cette%20%C3%A9tude,ni%C3%A9bé%20en%20condition%20de%20champ>
76. Ahmad J, Khan I, Ahmad A, and Imam K. *In Vitro* antioxidant and antimicrobial activity of methanolic root extracts of *Hyptis suaveolens*. *Res J Recent Sci.* 2013; 2: 41-46. Available at: <http://www.isca.in/rjrs/archive/v2/iISC-2012/9.ISCA-ISC-2012-03BS-85.php>
77. Shaikat ZH, Hossain T, and Azam G. Phytochemical screening and anti-diarrhoeal activity of *Hyptis suaveolens*. *Int J Appl Res Nat Prod.* 2012; 5(2): 1-4. Available at: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=e2fe598b586af0d1897457a4228412fd8479cf9d>
78. Praveen Nayak S, Nayak S, Kar DM, and Das P. *In vitro* antihelmintic activity of whole plant extracts of *Hyptis suaveolens* Poit. *Int J Curr Pharm Res.* 2010; 2(2): 5051.
79. Boni BY, Komlan AF, Mensah A, Taofic A, Verheggen F, and Frédéric F. *Plantespesticides et protection des cultures maraichères en Afrique de l'Ouest (synthèse bibliographique)* [Pesticide plants and protection of market garden crops in West Africa (literature review)]. *Biotechnol Agron Soc Environ.* 2017; 21(4): 288-304. DOI: [10.25518/1780-4507.16175](https://doi.org/10.25518/1780-4507.16175)